
APPLICATION OF AMPHIBOLE CHEMISTRY IN DETERMINING THE PETROGENESIS OF
HORNBLENDE-BIOTITE GRANITES FROM TORO COMPLEX, NORTHCENTRAL, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

Amphibole chemistry of the hornblende-biotite (HB) and porphyritic hornblende-biotite (PHB) granites from Toro, North-central Nigeria has been studied by electron probe micro analysis, to determine its petrogenesis. Generally, the amphiboles are calcic with a wide compositional range. The amphiboles in the Toro hornblende-biotite (HB) granite are mainly hastingsite and with minor ferro-tschermakite, while the Toro porphyritic hornblende-biotite (PHB) granite clustered between hastingsite and ferro-pargasite. Their thermobarometry shows that they were emplaced under low fO_2 , medium temperature (HB=771° to 633° C; 5.7 to 8.9 Kbar; PHB=775° to 714° C) and high pressure (HB=5.7 to 8.9 Kbar; PHB=6.0 to 6.6 Kbar). They plot in the igneous field of Ca+Na+K versus Si (apfu) diagram, which affirms that amphiboles of the studied rocks are of igneous origin as opposed to the metasomatic origin claimed to have been proposed by Oyawoye, (1962).

KEYWORDS: Petrogenesis, geothermobarometry, hornblende-biotitegranite, amphibole chemistry, Toro complex, north central Nigeria.

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INTRODUCTION

The Toro circular complex (Figure 1) is situated in north central Nigeria. It occupies a low hilly area above the surrounding Basement Complex about 2km NE of the Jos Younger Granites magmatic centre. According to Dada et al. (1989), Toro complex forms a near circular complex, of about 9 km across and is composed of granitoids: hornblende-biotite porphyries, fine and medium-grained biotite granite, even-grained hornblende biotite granite, porphyritic biotite and biotite-hornblende granite and hypersthene-diorite (Oyawoye, 1972; Deleris et al., 1986; Ashano et al., 2010; Figure 1). The inner ring (hornblende-biotite and porphyritic hornblende-biotite) granites show a sharp contact with diorite, but marginal exposures against the diorite are dark and mottled due to contamination (granodioritic). The outer ring differs from the other granite types by the absence of hornblende and its characteristic foliation is parallel to its margins (Ashano et al., 2010).

The Complex was formed by the initial intrusion of the medium-grained porphyritic granite (inner ring) whose outer sheared margin is now represented by the outer ring, with the subsequent intrusion of the coarse grained, equigranular granite between the outer sheared portion and the inner more massive portion.

The biotite composition of diorite from the complex has been studied by Dada and Ashano, (2012). They suggested that the diorite are formed from transition between peraluminous and calc-alkaline magmas (Dada and Ashano, 2012). Also, various origins have been proposed for the rocks of this complex from metasomatic origin (Oyawoye, 1962) to igneous origin (Dada et al., 1989). Thus, this study seeks to investigate and establish the origin of the hornblende-biotite granites from Toro complex, using its mineral chemistry.

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MATERIALS AND METHODS

Polish thin sections were made from rock selected fresh surface samples taken from the study area. The samples were analyzed using JXA JEOL- 8900L electron probe micro analyzer at the Electron Microprobe Laboratory, McGill University, Montreal, Canada. Amphibole analysis was conducted with a 15 Kv accelerating voltage, 20 nA beam current and a 10 um beam diameter. Natural minerals were used as standards and counting times at each peak was 20 seconds and background for all elements.

Figure 1: Geological Map of Toro Complex (Modified from Oyawoye, (1972); Deleris et al., (1986); Ashano et al., (2010).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

MINERAL CHEMISTRY

Representative and average microprobe analysis of amphiboles from hornblende-biotite and porphyritic hornblende-biotite granites are given in Tables 1 and 2. Structural formulae of amphiboles from Bauchi and Saminaka charnockites were calculated on an anhydrous basis assuming 23 Oxygens atoms per half unit cell, with the general form $A_{0.1}B_2C_5T_8O_{22}(OH)_2$ representing one formula unit.

Table 1: Representative amphibole compositions of the investigated hornblende-biotite granite

Sample no	HB91	HB92	HB93	HB94	HB95	HB96	HB97	HB98	HB99	HB100
SiO ₂	39.69	40.00	39.86	40.50	39.86	41.52	40.93	39.84	40.62	38.25
TiO ₂	1.66	1.32	1.33	1.54	1.19	1.58	1.51	1.14	1.22	0.65
Al ₂ O ₃	10.81	10.35	10.48	10.49	10.93	10.21	10.26	10.94	10.36	13.13
Cr ₂ O ₃	0.04	0.01	0.06	0.00	0.10	0.01	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.00
Fe ₂ O ₃	7.83	3.84	3.19	5.97	4.83	5.44	3.37	6.33	4.47	5.79
FeO	26.46	26.32	26.72	27.09	26.83	27.11	26.39	26.94	26.40	27.63
MnO	0.68	0.55	0.52	0.59	0.58	0.52	0.54	0.61	0.41	0.49
MgO	4.32	4.33	4.24	4.56	4.14	4.60	4.60	4.22	4.63	3.64
CaO	11.43	11.26	11.16	11.27	11.49	11.14	11.59	11.19	11.35	11.19
Na ₂ O	0.36	1.66	2.22	1.49	1.35	1.49	1.48	1.30	1.41	2.18
K ₂ O	1.36	1.51	1.55	1.55	1.62	1.59	1.63	1.59	1.65	1.90
H ₂ O*	1.91	1.89	1.90	1.94	1.91	1.95	1.93	1.91	1.92	1.92
O=F,Cl	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total	99.51	99.59	100.36	101.62	100.48	102.27	101.24	100.32	100.41	101.56
No. of O ₂	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23	23
Si	6.227	6.331	6.291	6.27	6.257	6.371	6.367	6.245	6.356	5.979
Al ^{IV}	1.773	1.669	1.709	1.73	1.743	1.629	1.633	1.755	1.644	2.021
	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
Al ^{VI}	0.226	0.262	0.241	0.184	0.279	0.218	0.248	0.267	0.267	0.398
Ti	0.196	0.157	0.158	0.179	0.141	0.182	0.177	0.134	0.144	0.076
Cr	0.005	0.001	0.007	0	0.012	0.001	0.005	0	0	0
Fe ³⁺	0.925	0.457	0.379	0.696	0.57	0.628	0.394	0.747	0.526	0.681
Fe ²⁺	2.547	3.027	3.148	2.811	2.952	2.851	3.038	2.785	2.929	2.931
Mn	0.09	0.074	0.07	0.077	0.077	0.068	0.071	0.081	0.054	0.065
Mg	1.01	1.022	0.998	1.052	0.969	1.052	1.067	0.986	1.08	0.848
	4.999	5	5.001	4.999	5	5	5	5	5	4.999
Ca	1.921	1.91	1.887	1.869	1.932	1.831	1.932	1.879	1.903	1.874
Na	0.11	0.509	0.679	0.447	0.411	0.443	0.446	0.395	0.428	0.661
K	0.272	0.305	0.312	0.306	0.324	0.311	0.323	0.318	0.329	0.379
	2.303	2.724	2.878	2.622	2.667	2.585	2.701	2.592	2.66	2.914
OH*	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Total	17.303	17.724	17.879	17.623	17.668	17.586	17.701	17.593	17.66	17.914
(Ca+Na) ^B	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000
Na ^B	0.079	0.090	0.113	0.131	0.068	0.169	0.068	0.121	0.097	0.126
(Na+K) ^A	0.303	0.724	0.879	0.623	0.668	0.586	0.701	0.593	0.660	0.914
Mg/(Mg+Fe ²⁺)	0.284	0.252	0.241	0.272	0.247	0.270	0.260	0.262	0.269	0.224
Fe ³⁺ /(Fe ³⁺ +Al ^{VI})	0.803	0.636	0.612	0.791	0.671	0.743	0.614	0.737	0.663	0.631
Fe/(Fe+Mg)	0.775	0.773	0.779	0.769	0.784	0.768	0.763	0.782	0.762	0.810

Table 2: Representative amphibole compositions of the investigated Toro porphyritic hornblende-biotite granite

Sample no	PHB51	PHB52	PHB53	PHB54	PHB55	PHB56	PHB57
SiO ₂	39.21	40.37	40.53	40.42	40.43	40.46	40.44
TiO ₂	1.62	1.49	1.42	1.43	1.59	1.46	1.50
Al ₂ O ₃	10.64	10.73	10.30	10.37	10.67	10.76	10.29
Cr ₂ O ₃	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.04	0.11	0.07	0.00
Fe ₂ O ₃	2.71	3.26	1.72	2.67	2.92	3.57	2.99
FeO	25.00	25.44	24.95	24.90	25.54	25.89	26.54
MnO	0.40	0.38	0.35	0.47	0.44	0.55	0.45
MgO	4.47	4.51	4.54	4.72	4.24	4.27	4.40
CaO	11.10	11.16	11.23	11.24	11.08	11.09	11.31
Na ₂ O	1.57	1.46	1.56	1.47	1.48	1.47	1.86
K ₂ O	1.70	1.59	1.51	1.55	1.53	1.72	1.63
H ₂ O*	1.87	1.90	1.88	1.89	1.90	1.91	1.91
O=F,Cl	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00
Total	97.87	99.36	98.45	98.77	99.30	100.01	100.63
No. of O ₂	23	23	23	23	23	23	23
Si	6.301	6.365	6.452	6.407	6.383	6.354	6.347
Al ^{IV}	1.699	1.635	1.548	1.593	1.617	1.646	1.653
	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
Al ^{VI}	0.316	0.358	0.384	0.345	0.369	0.346	0.25
Ti	0.196	0.177	0.17	0.171	0.189	0.172	0.177
Cr	0.003	0	0	0.005	0.14	0.009	0
Fe ³⁺	0.328	0.387	0.206	0.318	0.347	0.422	0.353
Fe ²⁺	3.032	2.967	3.116	2.983	3.025	2.978	3.131
Mn	0.054	0.051	0.047	0.063	0.059	0.073	0.06
Mg	1.07	1.06	1.077	1.115	0.998	1	1.029
	4.999	5	5	5	5.127	5	5
Ca	1.911	1.885	1.915	1.909	1.874	1.866	1.902
Na	0.489	0.446	0.481	0.452	0.453	0.448	0.566
K	0.349	0.32	0.307	0.313	0.308	0.345	0.326
	2.749	2.651	2.703	2.674	2.635	2.659	2.794
OH*	2	2	2	2	2	2	2
Total	17.749	17.651	17.703	17.674	17.635	17.658	17.794
(Ca+Na) ^B	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000	2.000
Na ^B	0.089	0.115	0.085	0.091	0.126	0.134	0.098
(Na+K) ^A	0.749	0.651	0.703	0.674	0.635	0.658	0.794
Mg/(Mg+Fe ²⁺)	0.261	0.263	0.257	0.272	0.248	0.251	0.247
Fe ³⁺ /(Fe ³⁺ +Al ^{VI})	0.509	0.519	0.349	0.480	0.485	0.550	0.585
Fe/(Fe+Mg)	0.759	0.760	0.755	0.748	0.772	0.773	0.772

Hornblende-biotite granite

According to the IMA classification and Fe^{3+} calculation proposed by Leake et al., (1997), all the amphiboles from hornblende-biotite granites are calcic ($\text{Ca}_B > 1.5$ apfu; Figure 4; Table 1) and belong to a sub group, where $(\text{Na}+\text{K})_A \geq 0.50$ apfu and $\text{Ti} < 0.50$ (Figure 2). This group mostly contains low Si contents ($^{\text{T}}\text{Si} < 6.5$), which is the characteristic of hastingsite, except for sample HB91 that belongs to the second subgroup which is defined by $(\text{Na}+\text{K})_A < 0.5$ apfu (Figure 2). This group mostly is characteristics of ferro-tschermakite. From the Si vs Mg / (Mg+Fe) diagram after Leake et al., (1997) used to classify the calcic amphibole, it is observed that the amphiboles are hastingsitic, except for sample HB91 which is ferrotschermakite (Figure 2). The amphiboles on average are rich in $\text{FeO}_{(\text{total})}$ while MgO is relatively low. FeO_T contents are high, range from 26.70 to 28.21% and are characterized by a low Fe^{3+} and a high Fe^{2+} contents (Tables 1-2).

Al_2O_3 is around 10% and all samples exhibit low Al^{VI} and high Al^{IV} contents which equates to more than 85% of Al in the tetrahedral site. All the analysed amphiboles contain sufficient Al to balance the Si deficiency in the tetrahedral sites. Na and K contents are low, with Na ranging between 0.110 and 0.679 apfu. Ca ranges from 1.831 to 1.932 apfu and Ti is very low, < 0.25 apfu. Regardless of the amount of Na+K in the A site, the XMg [$\text{Mg}/(\text{Mg}+\text{Fe}^{2+})$] ranges from 0.224 to 0.284, making them all ferroan.

Porphyritic Hornblende-biotite granite

The amphiboles from porphyritic hornblende-biotite granites are also calcic ($\text{Ca}_B > 1.5$ apfu; Figure 4; Table 1) and belong to the first sub group (Figure 2). The first group is defined by $(\text{Na}+\text{K})_A \geq 0.5$ apfu (Figure 2) and mostly contains low Si contents ($^{\text{T}}\text{Si} < 6.5$ apfu) which is characteristics of hastingsite and ferro-pargasite. From Si vs Mg / (Mg+Fe) diagram after Leake, (1997) used to classify the calcic amphibole, it is observed that the amphiboles straddle hastingsite and ferro-pargasite (Figure 2).

The amphiboles have high FeO_T contents and are characterized by a low Fe^{3+} and a high Fe^{2+} contents. The $\text{Fe}^{3+}/(\text{Fe}^{2+} + \text{Fe}^{3+})$ ratio ranges from 0.02 to 0.12. The XMg [$\text{Mg}/(\text{Mg}+\text{Fe}^{2+})$] ranges from 0.247 to 0.272, making them all ferroan. Ti content is very low ($\text{Ti} < 0.25$ apfu). TiO_2 contents range from 1.42 to 1.62%.

Al_2O_3 is around 10% and all samples exhibit low Al^{VI} and high Al^{IV} contents which equates to more than 80% of Al in the tetrahedral site which adequately balances the Si deficiency in the tetrahedral sites. It has high content of Na and K cations. Na content in most of the samples ranges from 0.446 - 0.566 apfu while K content ranges from 0.307 - 0.349 apfu. It exhibits low Ca values which range from 1.866 to 1.915 apfu.

AMPHIBOLE GEOTHERMOBAROMETRY

Several studies have dealt with parageneses of calcic amphibole in mafic (meta-) igneous rocks (Allen et al.,(1975); Allen and Boettcher,(1978); Helz,(1973); Spear (1981); Ernst and Liu,(1998)). These studies make it clear that, with increasing *P-T* conditions, calcic amphiboles exhibit increases in Mg/ (Mg + Fe) and in K, Al, Na, and Ti contents and commensurate decreases in Si and total Fe + Mg + Mn + Ca.

Pressure conditions of crystallization, deduced from contact aureoles or experimentally controlled runs have been observed to be correlated linearly with the Al-content in amphibole, and, many calibrations of the Al-in-amphibole barometer have been published (Hammarstrom and Zen,(1986); Hollister et al.,(1987); Johnson and Rutherford,(1988); Rutter,(1989); Blundy and Holland,(1990); Schmidt,(1992); Anderson and Smith,(1995); Ernst and Liu,(1998)).

Pressures for the mineral assemblages used in the temperature calculations were calculated using Al-in-hornblende method and equations proposed by different authors such as $P_1 = \text{Hammarstrom and Zen, (1986)}$; $P_2 = \text{Hollister et al., (1987)}$; $P_3 = \text{Schmidt, (1992)}$; Table 3). The results obtained from the Al-in-hornblende geobarometer and thermometer are given in Table 3. Calculated average pressures using geobarometers give values of $P_1 = 6.1$ Kbar; $P_2 = 6.4$ Kbar and $P_3 = 6.5$ Kbar for hornblende-biotite (HB) granite and $P_1 = 6.0$ Kbar; $P_2 = 6.3$ Kbar; $P_3 = 6.4$ Kbar for porphyritic hornblende-biotite (PHB) (Table 3). These pressures correspond to formation depth of 19km to 24km.

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GEOTHERMOMETRY

Electron microprobe data for the amphiboles from hornblende-biotite (HB) granite and porphyritic hornblende-biotite (PHB) granite from Toro complex were used to determine temperature of formation using temperature calibration based on Ti content in hornblende by Otten, (1984). This is best used to determine magmatic versus secondary composition. Temperature of formation estimates for hornblende-biotite (HB) granite vary from 633° to 771° C and 726° to 775° C for porphyritic hornblende-biotite (PHB) granite. The average temperature got from amphiboles from Toro hornblende-biotite (HB) granite is 725° C and 751° C for Toro porphyritic hornblende-biotite (PHB) granite. The temperatures difference may indicate a long interval of crystallization of the granites. Figure 3 adapted from Giret et al., (1980) shows that both granitoids have high temperature igneous amphiboles and not low temperature metamorphic amphiboles, indicating a formation as a result of igneous processes.

Table 3 shows Pressure Calculations using Hammarstrom and Zen, (1986), Hollister et al., (1987) and Schmidt, (1992).

Table 3: Results of geobarometry, Amph-Al (Total) of samples from hornblende-biotite (HB) granite and porphyritic hornblende-biotite (PHB) granite from Toro complex, North-central Nigeria.

Pressure	Hammarstrom & Zen (1986) P ₁	Hollister et al. (1987) P ₂	Schmidt (1992) P ₃
Toro hornblende-biotite granite (HB)			
Max (Kbar)	8.2	8.9	8.5
Min (Kbar)	5.4	5.7	5.8
Ave. (Kbar)	6.1	6.4	6.5
Toro porphyritic hornblende-biotite granite (PHB)			
Max (Kbar)	6.2	6.6	6.6
Min (Kbar)	5.7	6.0	6.1
Ave. (Kbar)	6.0	6.3	6.4

Table 4: Calculated temperature using amphibole population in hornblende-biotite (HB) granite and porphyritic hornblende-biotite (PHB) granite from Toro complex, north-central Nigeria (Ti-Hbd geothermometer of Otten, 1984).

Temperature	Max (°C)	Min (°C)	Average (°C)
Toro hornblende-biotite (HB) granite	771	633	725
Toro porphyritic hornblende-biotite (PHB) granite	775	726	751

DISCUSSION

Based on the IMA classification proposed by Leake et al., (1997), the amphiboles of Toro hornblende-biotite (HB) granite and Toro porphyritic hornblende-biotite (PHB) granite are calcic amphiboles (Figure 4), but this represented a wide compositional range. The amphiboles in the Toro hornblende-biotite (HB) granite are mainly hastingsite with minor ferro-tschermakite, while those in the Toro porphyritic hornblende-biotite (PHB) granite clustered between hastingsite and ferro-pargasite in the (Mg/ Mg + Fe²⁺) versus Si diagram (Figure 2).

The (Ca + Na + K) versus (Si) plot allows chemical discrimination between igneous and metamorphic amphiboles (Figure 3; Giret et al., 1980), which shows that all samples analyzed have high temperature igneous amphibole relative to low temperature metamorphic amphibole; this means that the analysed amphiboles were formed as a

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result of igneous processes. This behavior implies that the Toro hornblende-biotite (HB) and porphyritic hornblende-biotite (PHB) granites could not have been formed by metasomatic processes as suggested by Oyawoye's model (1962, 1964). Rather, the process of magmatic intrusion into the pre-existing older rocks as suggested by the Dada *et al.*, model (1989) must have been responsible for the emplacement.

From the Fe/(Fe + Mg) versus Al (apfu) diagram for fO₂ phases, the granites were at the boundary between low and intermediate fO₂ phase (Figure 5).

The calcic amphiboles in the granites crystallized at relatively medium pressures (Table 3; HB= 5.7 - 8.9 and PHB=6.0 - 6.6). Similar to crystallization pressure, temperatures (Table 4) are also sensitive to the nature and habit of crystals. Temperatures vary according to amphibole mean compositions (as well as XMg), and show a large range of values from 771° to 633 °C (HB) and 775° to 726° C (PHB). The foregoing shows that the granites were formed at higher pressure and medium temperature ranges, though the porphyritic hornblende-biotite (PHB) granite has higher temperature. These may have resulted from magmatic differentiation by crystal fractionation, where magma solidifies; to form the granites over a range of temperature as each mineral begin to crystallize at different temperatures.

Figure 2: Compositional variations of calcic-amphibole from the Toro hornblende-biotite (HB) and porphyritic hornblende-biotite (PHB) granites, North central Nigeria. Cation proportions are per formula unit. Amphibole classification after Leake *et al.* (1997).

Figure 3: Compositional variations of amphibole from the Toro hornblende-biotite (HB) and porphyritic hornblende-biotite (PHB) granites, Northcentral Nigeria plotted in terms of cations (Ca+Na+K) vs Si (apfu) diagram after Giret et al., (1980).

Figure 4: Composition and classification of amphiboles (After Leake et al., 1997).

Figure 5. Composition of amphiboles from the Toro hornblende-biotite (HB) and porphyritic hornblende-biotite (PHB) granites, in term of Fe/ (Fe+Mg) versus Al^{IV} . Fields of fO_2 , and composition of hornblende from the Toro hornblende-biotite (HB) and porphyritic hornblende-biotite (PHB) granites, North central Nigeria after Anderson and Smith (1995).

CONCLUSIONS

Following the discussions, it can be inferred that the hornblende-biotite (HB) and porphyritic hornblende-biotite (PHB) granites from Toro Complex in the Basement terrain of North central Nigeria have an igneous origin and are calcic with a wide compositional range. The amphiboles in the hornblende-biotite (HB) granite are mainly hastingsitic, with minor ferro-tschermakite, while those of porphyritic hornblende-biotite (PHB) granite clustered between hastingsite and ferro-pargasite. The amphibole chemistry proves that the studied rocks have low-intermediate fO_2 (Figure 5), medium temperature and high pressure conditions. This suggests that they are granulitic in nature (Dada et. al., 1989).

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